

**THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF ENGLISH TEACHERS WITH
OVER-SIZED CLASS IN THE DIVISION OF
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The Lived Experiences of English Teachers with Over-Sized Class in the Division of Maguindanao II

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class in the Division of Maguindanao II for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: (1) How do the English teachers manage the over-sized class? (2) How do the English teachers deliver instruction in the over-sized class? (3) How the English teachers assess students learning in the over-sized class? (4) What are the effects of over-sized class to the English learnings of the students? (5) How the over-sized class affect the teaching performance of the teachers? (6) What are the suggested solutions to address the issues in over-sized classes? This research utilized qualitative method exploiting the phenomenological research design to describe the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class. The semi-structured interview and observation were utilized as an instrument of the study. Taking pictures during observation will be taken for describe the actual lived experiences of English teachers inside the classroom. In addition, Purposive sampling was used to determine the participants who came from Five secondary schools in the division of Maguindanao II with English Teachers who are holding over-sized classes. Based on the findings the participants encountered challenges in teaching over-sized class. These challenges were captured in the emergent themes such as difficulty in engaging students in group activities, controlling students' misbehavior, evaluation and providing individuals feedback and lastly, teachers' mental and emotional aspects. It was concluded that most of the participants encountered difficulties in teaching over-sized class which negatively affects the teaching performance and learning of the students despite the multiple strategies they employed in teaching. To address the challenges encountered by English teachers in over-sized class it is recommended that school administrator may provide enough classrooms and hire qualified teachers to decrease the class size and to lessen the burden of the teachers and students.

Keywords: *lived experiences of English teachers, over-sized classroom, delivery of instruction, teaching performance, English learning*

Introduction

One of the issues in the educational system is the over class sizes. Class size was a term used in education to denote the typical number of pupils in a class, according to Adeyemi (2008). A global problem that impedes effective teaching and learning is classroom overcrowding, according to Hachem and Mayor (2019). According to Corcoran et al. (1988), congestion and demanding workloads for teachers result in stressful working conditions for them and greater absenteeism rates.

For learning in a large class, teaching involves several different trades.. Teaching in a big class means always being aware of the gap between what was taught and what the students learned. As stated by Amarat (2011), one of the most significant issues of teachers in public schools experience is overcrowding in a classrooms.

The Department of Education has dealt with these shortfalls by authorizing incredibly huge class sizes in order to serve a growing student population. Teachers managing courses with 60 to 80 learners are no longer unusual in urban centers. The Philippines has some of the most crowded classrooms in Asia, the Institute for Statistics of the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) reports statistics. The development of overly large classes is one of the main causes of the drastic decline in the quality of education provided by our public schools.

A class with too many students has an adverse effect on both teaching and learning, regardless of how skilled the teacher may be. On the other hand, smaller classrooms allow more one-on-one interactions between students and teachers and allow teachers to spend less time managing the classroom and more time actual teaching. In order to satisfy each student's unique needs in the classroom, teachers must develop successful teaching techniques and put them into practice, (Mahanta, 2019).

Therefore, the current practice of having bigger classes in public schools violates the right to a better education that Filipino students are given by the Constitution. The right of teachers to fair salary and reasonable working conditions is also violated by oversize classes. A teacher managing a class of 70 children in the existing system is actually carrying the load of two teachers, but without earning any additional pay. Whereas, in The Magna Carta for Public School teachers, also known as R.A. No. 4760, states that teachers may work no more than six hours per day in the classroom and two hours per day on administrative tasks, for a total of eight hours per day.

In addition, In the Division of Maguindano II, where there are 39 Secondary Schools, 621 secondary school teachers and 33, 898 enrolled students and still counting for the school year 2022-2023. The number of teachers are not enough to cater the number of students. Moreover, Due to the large number of enrolled students, the student-teacher ratio is likewise not feasible. The quantity of teachers a school has on hand does not determine how the children are divided up.

Lastly, the Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education emphasized on the Bangsamoro Education Code (BEC) “No Bangsamoro Children shall left behind”. Therefore, the researcher will find out the experiences of teachers with over-sized class in selected schools in the division of Maguindanao II.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the lived experiences of the English teachers with over-sized class in Maguindanao II Division during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do the English teachers manage the over-sized class?
2. How do the English teachers deliver instruction in the over-sized class?
3. How the English teachers assess students learning in the over-sized class?
4. What are the effects of over-sized class to the English learnings of the students?
5. How the over-sized class affect the teaching performance of the teachers?
6. What are the suggested solutions to address the issues in over-sized classes?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative method utilizing the phenomenological research design to describe the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class. Using this particular design would be able to achieve the result that the researcher is aiming for.

According to Busetto, Wick, and Gumbinger (2020), qualitative research was the study of a phenomenon's nature and is particularly suitable for addressing why a phenomenon is not observed, evaluating complex multi-component interventions, and concentrating on improving interventions. The definition of qualitative research is the study of the characteristics of phenomena, excluding their range, frequency, and position in an objectively determined cause-and-effect chain, but including their quality, various manifestations, context in which they arise, or perspectives from which they can be observed.

In addition Creswell (2013), explained a phenomenological study, on how a notion or occurrence is seen by many people to be in common with one another based on their personal experience. Phenomenology is a method of enquiry that seeks to understand a phenomenon from the perspective of participants' descriptions of their own human experiences.

Furthermore, Phenomenological research, as cited by Delve and Limpaecher (2022), is a qualitative research strategy that aims to comprehend and characterize the fundamental elements of a phenomenon. The methodology examined human experience in daily life while putting aside the researchers' prior notions about the phenomenon. In other words, phenomenology research investigates actual events to learn more about how people interpret them.

According to its definition, phenomenology is a field of study that focuses on how individuals view their surroundings and what they signify to them, (Langdrige, 2007). Furthermore, Phenomenology is a method for discovering both the hidden meanings and the essences of experience, (Grbich, 2007).

In this study, the design was utilized to describe and understand the lived experiences of English teachers towards handling over-sized classes. The participant's experiences in managing large classes were the basis for the researcher's information collection during in-depth interviews, which were conducted with them. According to Gamarang (2021), the main objective of phenomenology, a 20th-century philosophical idea, is to thoroughly explore and describe phenomena as they are actually experienced, without making assumptions about their causes or effects, and without unjustified assumptions and prejudices.

The researcher used Colaizzi's methodology for descriptive phenomenology to evaluate the data thematically to get a general understanding of the content, each transcript should be read several times. Important statements that are relevant to the phenomenon being studied should be taken out of each transcript. The significance of these statements must be noted on a separate sheet along with their page and line numbers. From these significant statements, meanings should be formulated; the formulated meanings should then be categorized into categories, clusters of themes, and themes. The study's findings must be incorporated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study, along with a description of the phenomenon's basic structure.

Moreover, this paper concentrated on describing the participants' actual experiences and giving context to the experiences that were connected to the phenomena analyzing any procedure relating to the participants' experiences.

Participants

The participants of this study were 5 English teachers from the Maguindanao II Division. The researcher utilized purposive sampling in identifying the English teachers as the participants of the study. This sampling technique in qualitative research design use to recruit participants who can provide in-depth and detailed information about the phenomenon under investigation. Furthermore, the participants were purposively selected since they are handling classes that exceed to ideal number of students per class. To emphasize, it was stated in Department of Education Order no. 21 series of 2006, the ideal class size shall range from a minimum of 15 students

to a maximum of 65 students per class. The ideal average class size shall be 50. The participants were selected since they exceed the maximum class size.

In order to protect the participants from any harm or prejudices that may be caused by the culturally sensitive problem or information that would be revealed during the interviews, the participants' true identities were withheld out of respect for their privacy and in accordance with the research protocol.

As cited in Samson (2017), according to Mackenzie (2009), given how difficult and time-consuming data collecting is, it is anticipated that the sample size would be minimal. According to Ary, et al. (2006), the sample population for qualitative phenomenology is much smaller and has a higher level of analysis. Furthermore, Creswell (2007) suggests five (5) to twenty-five (25) people, while Morse (2000) suggests at least six (6) participants. Ten (10) participants for qualitative conforms the criterion. As a result, the researcher will have a stronger connection to the participants and the data that will be gathered, which will help them better describe and comprehend the phenomenon. These teachers have used a variety of teaching techniques to instruct the pupils and have experience managing large classes.

The first participant was Ma'am Rai, a graduate Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. She is currently a Grade 10 adviser with 83 students enrolled in her section. She is teaching English 10 subject and 3 loads at Senior High School. She is also the English Coordinator of their department at Datu Usngan S. Mastura National High School.

Second participant was Ma'am Lez, a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. She is a SPED class adviser with 45 students and have English subjects in three sections of Grade 10 with 66 students per section. She is one of the great teacher at Amir Bara Lidasan National High School.

Third participant was Sir Jun, a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. He is a Grade 9 adviser, SSG-Adviser and Yes-O Co-adviser. He is handling English subjects of three section of Grade 9 with 62 students. He is one of the active faculty of Sultan Mastura National High School.

Fourth participant was Sir Dan, a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. He is currently a Grade 7 adviser with 65 students. He is teaching English subject in for 4 section, he is also the chairman of campus journalism at Making Integrated Vocational School.

Lastly, Ma'am Sha a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. She is a Grade 8 adviser with 102 students. She is teaching English subjects in 3 sections. Ma'am sha is known as active teacher of Nuling National High school.

Instruments

The semi-structured interview and observation were utilized as an instrument of the study. These two combination of method are types of qualitative research design used to gain deep contextual understanding of the phenomena and will rely on the direct experiences of the respondents. Taking pictures during observation were taken to describe the lived experiences of English teachers with over-size class.

Gumarang (2021) stated that a semi-structured in-depth interview was the major method utilized to gather information and obtain reliable and factual data through face-to-face. Each interview lasted 20 to 30 minutes. The interview started off with general inquiries but moved further with a relaxed and adaptable style. The participants' degree of engagement actually determined how the interview went.

Furthermore, In-depth, semi-structured interviews are widely utilized as an interview format, sometimes with a single subject and other times with a group according to Pharm (2014), these interviews, which can be performed with an individual or a group only once, often run between 30 minutes and over an hour. Following a series of open-ended questions, participants in a semi-structured interview are then asked more questions to delve deeper into their responses and the research topic. Semi-structured interviews in qualitative research combine the most beneficial elements of structured and unstructured interviews. While some questions lack preset answers, others do.

Semi-structured interviews provide you the opportunity to explore any relevant ideas that may arise while the interview is still going on, while still allowing you to concentrate on the topic of interest. Semi-structured interviews are a typical method employed by qualitative researchers to collect new data and gauge participant perspectives on a certain topic.

As defined by Langdrige (2007), the semi-structured interview format contained questions with open-ended follow-ups and suggestions. Participants were urged to interpret their experiences by employing focusing. In order to help participants' memory recall, this interviewing style shifts from general queries to more focused inquiries about topics of particular interest, Noon, et all (2018).

The researcher will also make use of qualitative observation to provide them a richer picture of the individuals in their natural setting. The methods, culture, or subjects of the study can all be better understood thanks to this form of data collection.

Different sources of evidence, such as content validity evidence, could be analyzed to determine the validity of the instrument. According to Beck and Gable (2001) as cited by Samson (2007), the importance of content validity emphasizes how well an instrument's items capture its subject matter. They propose that content validity be assessed while the instrument is being developed rather than

after it has been finalized.

Procedure

In the context of research ethics, the informed consent of each teacher participating in the study to make sure they understand what they would be undertaking and to confirm their readiness to participate in the study. A letter of permission will be sent to the Division of Maguindanao II and to the school heads of the selected schools for the conduct of the study.

All participants in the study gave their consent and were not coerced into taking part. Participants were given guarantees that they would not face any danger, shame, excessive stress, or humiliating treatment throughout the procedure. We pledged and upheld secrecy and anonymity. Participants were also assured that their identities would be kept confidential during the whole study.

Since the respondents are fluent in English, the semi-structured in-depth interview was conducted in that language. However, they were given the freedom to respond to the questions in any other language, including Filipino or their native tongue, if they felt more comfortable doing so, in order to ensure the richness of the data. The interview for teachers included both closed-ended and open-ended questions to help the researchers follow up on topics that needed explanation and to help the respondents understand questions that were unclear to them.

A Huawei cellular phone model YAL-L21 was used to record and captured the details of the interview and observations. A unit have features of internal memory of 128GB, 8GB RAM. Assisting the investigator during the interview was one of her colleagues in the target school. Every interview was audio recorded by the researcher with the subject's consent. The date and interviewee number were appropriately coded into each interview.

There was a distinct file for each interview. The interview code given to each interview served as its label. Following the interview, the researcher listened to the recording, take notes, and transcribed the data gathered. Furthermore, the analysis of related literature further verified the consistency of the data the researchers provided readings that either support or refute the shared lived experiences of study participants.

Consequently, the investigator heard the participants' makes up without bias, establishing the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class gathered during the interview.

To protect the participants' rights, it was crucial for the investigator to uphold secrecy and privacy. This is the reason why the study withholds the participants' real names. The data gathered should be used solely for the purpose of the study. The verbatim transcriptions of the audio-recorded interviews collected during the interview were completed. All data were coded that only the investigator has the access to the privacy of the information. Respect was shown for difficulties encountered over the course of the study, such as dealing with individuals who did not satisfy the criteria for inclusion and delays in response to request letters. Prior to data collection, statements of protecting the participants' rights were created, written, and given to each participant.

To establish a sense of belonging and provide the participants a sense that they were a part of the endeavor, the investigator observed inclusion of all participants throughout the research process. Only valid information from the interviews was recorded, interpreted, and presented. Data modification was not permitted in any way. Due to this, each written transcript and interpretation was personally returned to each participant and explained for review and confirmation.

Data Analysis

The methodology of Colaizzi (1978), as cited by Samson (2017), was employed to analyze the phenomenological data that were acquired for this study. The Colaizzi's method was centered on investigating and comprehending participants' actual encounters with the phenomenon. According to Speziale and Carpenter (2007), this technique can also be constructed in seven (7) procedural phases, which are as follows:

First, the researcher was engage in reading and re-reading of the transcript of the interview, second when the general picture of the whole content of each transcript was captures, the researcher extracted from each transcript the significant statements pertaining to the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized classes. On separate sheet, these significant statements were recorded keeping note of their pages and line numbers for convenient retrieval of the data as needed. Third, meanings from extracted significant statements from each transcript were formulated. Fourth, the meaning that were formulated by the researcher were sorted into categories, cluster themes and themes. Fifth, the themes which emerged from clustering procedures were integrated into a vivid description of the lived experiences in over-sized classes.

Finally, the participant-validation process was started after the researcher had finished describing the phenomenon's basic structure and had shown them the analyzed data. Another day was set by the researcher to meet the participants for validation of their transcripts of interviews. On the same day, the researcher explained the meaning of the participants experiences towards the phenomenon. The participants compared the researcher's descriptive results with their very own experiences. By signing the validation form, they conformed to the content of their individual transcript as well as to the researcher's description of fundamental structure of their experiences.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the phenomenological data gathered to achieve the objective of the study. The data were taken from audio recordings of the in-depth interview of the Five (5) English Teachers. These recordings were manually and digitally transcribed and translated into English.

Throughout the process of identifying significant statements from each transcripts of interviews to formulation of meanings and emergent themes that established the surfaced patterns formulated according to the influenced factors of the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class.

English Teachers Management Strategy of Over-sized Class

The significant statements, formulated meanings, code and theme of the participants' responses on what are the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class are reflected in Table 1.

Table 1. *English Teachers Management Strategy of Over-sized Class*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1	Of course by implementing classroom rules and regulations. If really the first thing to do before class start and should be strictly followed.	Classroom rules and regulation are imposed at beginning of the class	Implementing classroom rules and regulation	111
2	I imposed discipline of course. I am very strict on that. My students knows me well in terms of how my classroom should go when I am teaching. Everything must be settled before I begin my lecture. No messy things around, no extra-curricular activities allowed when my class begin.	Classroom rules and regulation are imposed at beginning of the class	Rules and regulation are imposed Implementing classroom rules and regulation	111
3	Through setting classroom rules and regulations. That's very important thing, imposing classroom rules and regulations.	Classroom rules and regulation are imposed at beginning of the class	Implementing classroom rules and regulation	111
4	Honestly, speaking, you can't manage them. That's the reality of teaching. You can't manage them, but you can minimize the misbehavior of the children. But when it come, when it comes in managing, you can manage but you can't control them. They have their own style in creating noise. And, and the fact (na hindi sila lahat nabibigyan ng pansin,) not all of them get attention, that's really one of the problems still existing now,	Students misbehavior are uncontrollable but manageable	Minimize the misbehavior of students	112
5	In terms of classroom management. I am very strict. I make sure that before the formal class begin I impose the rules and regulations that I want my students to strictly follow	Classroom rules and regulation are imposed at beginning of the class	Implementing classroom rules and regulation	111

The table 1 shows the gathered data from shared experiences of the participants on English teachers' management strategy of over-sized class. There are five themes emerged from the significant statements of the participants coded 111-115.

Four out of five participants, coded as 111 with emergent themes of implementing classroom rules and regulations. This means that implementing classroom rules and regulation will guide students on the first day of the class.

This implies that English teachers are implementing classroom rules and regulations at the beginning of the class as their management strategy in over-sized class. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participants 1, 2, 3 and 5, "Of course by implementing classroom rules and regulations. If really the first thing to do before class start and should be strictly followed"; "I imposed discipline of course. I am very strict on that. My students knows me well in terms of how my classroom should go when I am teaching. Everything must be settled before I begin my lecture. No messy things around, no extra-curricular activities allowed when my class begin"; "Through setting classroom rules and regulations. That's very important thing, imposing classroom rules and regulations"; and "In terms of classroom management. I am very strict. I make sure that before the formal class begin I impose the rules and regulations that I want my students to strictly follow".

This was supported by the idea of Adams (2003) stating that one of the methods used to promote excellent behavior in children is the

establishment of school rules and regulations. This entails maintaining self-control, maintaining order, acting appropriately, and obeying school authorities. Managing classrooms entails controlling the level of complexity in the group. It covers how to provide instructions, how to deal with disruptive students and stop it from happening again, as well as how to handle unforeseen circumstances that can disrupt the class.

One out of five participants coded as 112 with an emergent theme of minimizing the misbehavior of the students. This means that minimizing the misbehavior of students will guide students' actions on the first day of the class.

This implies that English teacher minimized the misbehavior of students are their classroom management strategy in over-sized class that will reduce disruptive behavior among students, promote healthy and beneficial social interactions among them, and provide a warm and comfortable physical environment for learning in the classroom. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 4, "In terms of classroom management. I am very strict. I make sure that before the formal class begin I impose the rules and regulations that I want my students to strictly follow".

To emphasize the idea, Affandi, et al. (2020) affirmed that that the basic goal of classroom management is to establish an atmosphere that supports learning, Classroom management seeks to decrease disruptive conduct among students, foster positive and useful social connections and provide a welcoming and healthy physical atmosphere for learning in the classroom.

English Teachers Manner/ Way of Delivering Instructions in Over-sized Class

The significant statements, formulated meanings, code and theme of the participants' responses on what are the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class are reflected in Table 2.

Table 2. *English Teachers Manner/ Way of Delivering Instructions in Over-sized Class*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1	In my part, I always think of right strategies and approach that will fit to their learning needs and will be applicable to everyone in the class.	Teachers find it hard to develop teaching strategies that will satisfy the different learning needs of the students in over-sized class.	Using differentiated instruction	211
2	By having different strategies on how to get their full attention. Because getting students interests is one of the hardest part of teaching. You have to adjust on their learning needs if you really want to make your teaching successful. Successful means all have understood the lesson and with over-sized class that we have. It's a triple and extra effort for us to think of a strategies that will surely meet the needs of the learners.	Teachers find it hard to develop teaching strategies that will satisfy the different learning needs of the students in over-sized class.	Using differentiated instruction	211
3	Honestly No, so what I am doing is, I do the distance learning or online class for me to meet and finish the topic on time.	Teachers use online teaching to meet and finish his topic on time	Conducting online teaching	212
4	So what I do, and I'm just so blessed and my subjects that I handle, I have lots of books in English, so everyone has the chance to have their own book. So what I do is atleast (nasusundan nila sa books kasi yun naman), they can follow it in books because that's it, if you cannot have the 21st century style of teaching that (methods-method na gusto natin na msyadong magaganda) that kind of methods that so very nice.	Teachers cannot execute the ideal class that they want like 21st century teaching and other teaching methods that they like to apply because of over-sized class.	Using books	213
5	Delivering your instruction in over-sized class is hard, you are like competing with who's the loudest of all. But what I do is, when I speak everyone should and must listen, no one is allowed to speak unless I ask them to speak and of course I always make sure that my voice is loud enough to hear clear enough to be understood.	Delivering your instruction in over-sized class is hard because of so much noise	Teach with modulated voice	214

The Table 2 shows the shared experiences on How English Teachers deliver instructions in over-sized class. There are five themes emerged from the significant statements of participants coded 211-215.

Two out of five participants coded as 211, with emergent themes of using differentiated instruction. This means that teachers used differentiated instructions as their ways in delivering instruction in over-sized class.

This implies that teachers used differentiated instruction in delivering instructions in over-sized class to satisfy the learning needs of different students. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participants 1 and 2, “In my part, I always think of right strategies and approach that will fit to their learning needs and will be applicable to everyone in the class”; and “By having different strategies on how to get their full attention. Because getting students interests is one of the hardest part of teaching. You have to adjust on their learning needs if you really want to make your teaching successful. Successful means all have understood the lesson and with over-sized class that we have. It’s a triple and extra effort for us to think of a strategies that will surely meet the needs of the learners”.

In support, Mahanta (2019) claims that in order to satisfy each student's unique needs in the classroom, teachers must develop successful teaching strategies and put them into practice and it is the duty of teachers to create a comprehensive teaching and learning environment that supports students' learning.

One out of five participant coded as 212 with an emergent theme of conducting online teaching. This means that the teacher was conducting online teaching as his way of delivering instruction in over-sized class.

This implies that conducting online class in over-sized class helps teachers meet the lessons to reduce learning losses. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 3, “Honestly No, so what I am doing is, I do the distance learning or online class for me to meet and finish the topic on time”.

In the same way, Kulal and Nayak (2020) cited that over the following few years, online learning will continue to expand significantly in both commercial and educational contexts. Because of the Internet and the World Wide Web, educational institutions have had to adapt their teaching methods in order to provide an optimum learning environment for their students. Online instruction fosters learning environments where students actively participate in the subject matter, gain information through application, and reflect on their understanding as they do so.

One out of five participant coded as 213 with an emergent theme of using books in teaching. This means that the teacher was using books as his way of delivering instruction in over-sized class. This implies that using books will help teacher and students to aid and supplement the learnings in over-sized class. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 4, “So what I do, and I'm just so blessed and my subjects that I handle, I have lots of books in English, so everyone has the chance to have their own book. So what I do is atleast (nasusundan nila sa books kasi yun naman), they can follow it in books because that’s it, if you cannot have the 21st century style of teaching that (methods-method na gusto natin na msyadong magaganda) that kind of methods that so very nice”.

Similarly, Tucker (2011), stated that teachers are faced with the challenging task of instructing students at all levels in a single class as class sizes increase tremendously. Teachers need to challenge and involve students who are academically excellent while also structuring the curriculum to accommodate students who are learning at lower proficiency levels. He also underlined that curriculum should be structured to accommodate students who are working at a lower level or those who have learning difficulties, both known and unknown.

One out five participant coded as 214 with the emergent theme of using modulated voice to be heard and understood by the students. This means that the teacher was using modulated voice as her way of delivering instruction in over-sized class. This implies that using modulated voice helps the teacher command the over-sized class. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 5, “Delivering your instruction in over-sized class is hard, you are like competing with who’s the loudest of all. But what I do is, when I speak everyone should and must listen, no one is allowed to speak unless I ask them to speak and of course I always make sure that my voice is loud enough to hear clear enough to be understood”.

Thus, Terada (2023) stated that one of the most effective weapons at your command for classroom management is your voice. Teachers speak to convey information through direct instruction, assess student comprehension through questions, help students move between activities, and regulate conduct by re-directing disobedient students and giving instructions as needed.

English Teachers Learning Assessment Strategies in Over-sized Class

The significant statements, formulated meanings, code and theme of the participants’ responses on what are the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class are reflected in Table 3.

The table 3 shows the gathered data from shared experiences of the participants on English teachers’ learning assessment strategies in over-sized class. There are five clustered themes emerged from significant statements of participants coded as 311-315.

Three out of five participants coded as 311 with the emergent themes of used formative assessments and feedbacking. This means that English teachers used formative assessment and feedbacking to monitor students learning and to improve students learning and teachers’ instructions. This implies that formative assessment is the tools used by English teachers in assessing the learnings of students in over-sized class. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 1, 2 and 5, “I used formative assessment and feedbacks. Whatever the result will justify the extent of learning that they had”, “Through their output such as quizzes Their output will tell if they learned or not”, “I used formative assessment and ask them for feedbacks regarding the topic”.

This supports the claim of Ferlazzo, (2021) that assessment is a key element of teaching that teachers need to identify students learning process, how effective the instructional strategies have been used, and if there are additional challenges that needs to be aware of as

planning future lessons and student support.

Table 3. *English Teachers Learning Assessment Strategies in Over-sized Class*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1	I used formative assessment and feedbacks. Whatever the result will justify the extent of learning that they had.	Teacher used formative assessment and feedbacks to measure the learnings of students.	Use of formative assessment and feedbacking	311
2	Through their output such as quizzes Their output will tell if they learned or not.	Teacher used outputs of the students to measure learnings of the students	Use of formative assessment and feedbacking	311
3	Through oral recitation and any other form of assessment like asking questions while the discussion is on going.	Teacher used oral recitation and asking questions to the students about the topic or learnings	Use of formative assessment	312
4	of course through summative and formative assessment. This form of assessment will give measurement level of learning of students. Asking about the topic through review of previous topic can also give feedback to the learnings of students.	Teacher used formative assessment and feedbacks to measure the learnings of students.	Use of Formative assessment and summative assment	313
5	I used formative assessment and ask them for feedbacks regarding the topic.	Teacher used formative assessment and feedbacks to measure the learnings of students.	Use of formative assessment and feedbacking	311

One out of five participant coded as 312 with emergent theme of using formative assessment. This means that the teacher used formative assessment in assessing students learning. It implies that using formative assessment to monitor how well a class is teaching. Better understanding and involvement among students may result from it. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 3, “Through oral recitation and any other form of assessment like asking questions while the discussion is on going”.

This was supported by the idea cited by Kulasegaram & Rangachari (2018) that formative assessment used to improve student learning and the growth of self-regulatory learning strategies, as cited by It is also an excellent approach for instructors and students.

One out of five participant coded as 313 with emergent theme of using formative and summative assessment. This means that using formative assessment and summative assessment will determine whether teaching is having an impact on students’ learning in over-sized class.

This implies that formative assessment and summative assessment are tools used by English teachers in assessing the learnings of students in over-sized class. Thus, assessments used in gathering data of students learning to better understand the strengths and weaknesses of students. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 4, “of course through summative and formative assessment. This form of assessment will give measurement level of learning of students. Asking about the topic through review of previous topic can also give feedback to the learnings of students”

The idea was supported by Stassen et al. (2001) that assessment is the methodical gathering and analysis of data for improving student learning. The essential duty of student evaluation in the teaching and learning process is covered in this description. Teachers can utilize student evaluation to assess the efficacy of their instruction by linking student performance to specific learning objectives. As a result, effective teaching strategies can be institutionalized by teachers, and ineffective ones can be changed in their pedagogy. Moreover, the evaluation of student learning is significant because it provides teachers and students with crucial knowledge about how well students are fulfilling the course's learning objectives.

Effects of Over-sized Class in English Learning of Students

The significant statements, formulated meanings, code and theme of the participants’ responses on what are the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class are reflected in Table 4.

The table 4 shows the gathered data from shared experiences of the participants on effects of over-sized class in English learnings of students. There are five clustered themes emerged from significant statements of participants coded as 411-415.

Three out of Five participants coded as 411 with emergent theme of difficulty in English learning. This means that the effects of over-sized class to students are difficulty in English learning. This implies that the effects of over-sized class to students are difficulty in English learning that hinders English learning. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participants 1, 3 and 5, “I don’t see any positive effect of English learning in over-sized class. Learning English especially grammar, you have to check it one by one if they could able to construct sentences but with over-sized class, you cannot do that”; “It is enjoyable and interesting, I mean the more

the merrier. You can do group activities that they will surely enjoy like, drama, dance”; “the only positive things that I can see in teaching over-sized class is that in sharing wisdom, more heads are better because more heads can listen, but in learning English, I don’t see any positive effects”.

Table 4. *Effects of Over-sized Class in English Learning of Students*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1	I don’t see any positive effect of English learning in over-sized class. Learning English especially grammar, you have to check it one by one if they could able to construct sentences but with over-sized class, you cannot do that.	Teachers do not see positive effects on the English learnings of the students especially in learning grammar	Difficulty in learning English	411
2	if they like the lesson and activities they participate, specially if there is attachment of it in real life situations. The only positive effects that I see is if you want to have a group activities that needs more members then over-sized class is very practical.	Over-sized class is suitable in group activities that requires many members and learnings becomes participative when relating to real life situations	Minimum learning	412
3	It is enjoyable and interesting, I mean the more the merrier. You can do group activities that they will surely enjoy like, drama, dance presentation and others	Over-sized class is suitable in group activities that requires many members and learnings becomes participative when relating to real life situations	Difficulty in learning English	411
4	Positive, Many students will learn from you, that’s it. We can’t assure that all them really learn from you. But if we are talking about over-sized, there is nothing positive effects. For me. If we want quality and engaging classroom set up, its not ideal, most specially in english I don’t see any positive.	Teachers do not see positive effects on the English learnings of the students especially in learning grammar	Over-sized class hinders English learning	413
5	the only positive things that I can see in teaching over-sized class is that in sharing wisdom, more heads are better because more heads can listen, but in learning English, I don’t see any positive effects.	Teachers do not see positive effects on the English learnings of the students especially in learning grammar	Difficulty in learning English	411

In the same way Russell & Curtis, (2013), identified that class size may also have an effect on other elements of effective language learning, including: given the time required for a comprehensive assessment of student progress toward increasing language proficiency using tools like Integrated Performance Assessment; ability to provide students with enough feedback to help them achieve their learning objectives, quality and quantity of student-student and student-teacher interaction, ability to decrease students' affective filters and promote self-assurance when speaking the target language

One out of five participant coded as 412 with the emergent theme of minimum learning. This means that minimum learning is employed in over-sized class. This implies that the effects of over-sized class to students are minimum learning are employed hinders the English learning of students that certainly the primary cause of the declining quality of education. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participants 2, “if they like the lesson and activities they participate, especially if there is attachment of it in real life situations. The only positive effects that I see is if you want to have a group activities that needs more members then over-sized class is very practical”.

This support that claim of Adolphus & Godgift (2022) that class size was one of the factors influencing teaching and learning especially in Junior Secondary schools. As school population increases, class size also increases, the performance of students become a phenomenon often mentioned in educational literatures as an influence on teaching and learning.

One out of five participant coded as 413 with emergent theme of over-sized class hinders English learning. This means that over-sized class hinders English learning of the students. This implies that over-sized class hinders English learning of the students that certainly the primary cause of the declining quality of education. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participants 4, “Positive, Many students will learn from you, that’s it. We can’t assure that all them really learn from you. But if we are talking about over-sized, there is nothing positive effects. For me. If we want quality and engaging classroom set up, its not ideal, most specially in english I don’t see any positive”.

To emphasize the idea, language acquisition requires learners to be immersed in the target language while also being supported in their comprehension. While this is achievable in larger courses, it is challenging to give feedback and participate in open-ended communicative activities, Filges, et al (2018).

Effect of Over-sized Class in Teaching Performance of Teachers

The significant statements, formulated meanings, code and theme of the participants' responses on what are the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class are reflected in Table 5.

Table 5. *Effect of Over-sized Class in Teaching Performance of Teachers*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1	the positive side of over-sized class is more students will learn from you; the only negative thing is, not all will learn because of many factors that over-sized class have. Like involving them in activities.	Teachers see it positive when students learn from her however not all will learn because of many factors; such difficulty of involving students in activities	Failure to maximize facilitation of learning and giving of activities	511
2	Teachers' frustration come in when goals and expectations were not met. Its mentally draining for teachers handling over-sized class. You give your best but still not enough, that's why they don't learn.	Teachers get frustrated leads to become mentally drained in handling over-sized class.	frustration and mental draining	512
3	Classroom activities are not executed and performed well because of lack of space and a lot of heads to accommodate.	Teachers cannot implement activities and cannot teach well due to insufficient space	Failure to deliver quality instruction	513
4	emotionally draining and mentally exhausted? imagine a 65 Students your hand, okay, and they go you're not only dealing 65 speed and you rehab three sections. So 65 times three. So let's put it this way. We have 235 students, but yeah, Do you think it is not emotionally draining on your part? Most are mentally draining and then that 200 plus students are not don't don't have the same level of IQ? Now, you are now questioning your worth as a teacher am I doing things the right thing?	Teachers believe that over-sized class is emotionally and mentally draining on their part and questioning their teaching ability when students do not learn.	emotionally and mentally exhausted	514
5	Having over-sized class affects my teaching performance to the extent that, I can not implement the kind of teaching that I want, I cannot let my students perform some activities that needs enough space and it's really hard on my part. It feels like you cannot justify the learnings of the students.	Teachers cannot implement activities and cannot teach well due to insufficient space	Failure to deliver quality instruction	513

The table 5 shows the gathered data from shared experiences of the participants on effects of over-sized class to the teaching performance of teachers. There are five clustered themes emerged from significant statements of participants coded as 511-515.

One out five participants coded 511 with emergent theme of failure to maximize the facilitation of learning and giving of activities. This means that over-sized class failed to maximize the facilitation of learning and giving of activities. This implies that failure to maximize the facilitation of learning and giving of activities effects the teaching performance of English teachers. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 1, "the positive side of over-sized class is more students will learn from you; the only negative thing is, not all will learn because of many factors that over-sized class have. Like involving them in activities".

This support the claim of Fortes, (2010) every teacher faces a real challenges when dealing with large classes because of the diversity of the students, the lack of flexibility, the management of the classroom climate, the difficulty of setting and enforcing classroom rules (crowd control), the minimal attention given to each student, the limited monitoring of the students' learning, and the difficulty of involving the students in activities

Two out of five participant coded as 512 with emergent theme of frustration and mental draining. This means that teachers experiences frustration and mental draining in teaching over-sized class. This implies that teacher's experiences frustration and mental draining in teaching over-sized class affects their teaching performance. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 2, "Teachers' frustration come in when goals and expectations were not met. Its mentally draining for teachers handling over-sized class. You give your best but still not enough, that's why they don't learn".

It was supported by, Bahansha (2013) who recommended to investigate various approaches and putting them into practice in order to lessen the negative effects of large courses and raise the bar for both teaching and learning.

Two out of five participants coded as 513 with emergent theme of failure to deliver quality instruction. This means that teaching over-

sized class failed to deliver quality instruction. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 3 and 5, “Classroom activities are not executed and performed well because of lack of space and a lot of heads to accommodate”; “Having over-sized class affects my teaching performance to the extent that, I can not implement the kind of teaching that I want, I cannot let my students perform some activities that needs enough space and it’s really hard on my part. It feels like you cannot justify the learnings of the students”.

Rohin (2013) supported this ideas that teachers must increase their pedagogical understanding and adopt some successful teaching strategies, like group projects and jigsaw discussions.

One out of five participant coded as 514 with emergent theme of emotional and mentally exhausted. This means that teachers of over-sized emotional and mental exhausted. This implies that teachers of over-sized emotional and mental exhausted that effects their teaching performances. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 4, “emotionally draining and mentally exhausted? imagine a 65 Students your hand, okay, and they go you're not only dealing 65 speed and you rehab three sections. So 65 times three. So let's put it this way. We have 235 students, but yeah, Do you think it is not emotionally draining on your part? Most are mentally draining and then that 200 plus students are not don't don't have the same level of IQ? Now, you are now questioning your worth as a teacher am I doing things the right thing?”

This is supported by Xu (2011), who points out the problems which teacher encountered in large class, namely: discomfort, control, individual attention, evaluation and learning effectiveness. These problems could be problematic to the teachers, however learners themselves might think that it is not a problem.

Suggested Solutions to Address Issues on Over-sized Class

The significant statements, formulated meanings, code and theme of the participants’ responses on what are the lived experiences of English teachers with over-sized class are reflected in Table 6.

Table 6. *Suggested Solutions to Address Issues on Over-sized Class*

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Significant statements</i>	<i>Formulated Meanings</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1	I think to address this issues, our authorities should build more buildings and hire teachers so that, the burden of teachers will be lessen. Buildings and teachers are the only solutions	concern a authorities have to build classrooms and hire teachers to minimize the burden of teachers and students in over-sized class	Building classrooms and Hiring teachers	611
2	provide classrooms and teachers, why? Because if ever we have more classrooms and teachers, then we can divide over-sized classes. It will less burdens for the teachers.	Concern a authorities have to build classrooms and hire teachers to minimize the burden of teachers and students in over-sized class	Building classrooms and Hiring teachers	611
3	if they could provide us enough classrooms then better because that what students need so far of course teachers as well.	Concern a authorities have to build classrooms and hire teachers to minimize the burden of teachers and students in over-sized class	Building classrooms and hiring teachers	611
4	Okay to be honest, to those concern heads and authorities, they should give priorities in building classrooms and hiring more teachers so that we can follow the ideal number of students per classroom, by that way (pwede na natin e) apply yung we can apply that teaching approach that we want, execute fun learning activities. So if they want quality education then they should provide what is lacking in the school. (Syempre add to mo na din ang) of course you also add the free professional growth trainings for teachers because we really need that because we are molding young minds and the hope of future of the nation.	Concern a authorities have to build classrooms and hire teachers to minimize the burden of teachers and students in over-sized class	Building classrooms, hiring teachers and provisions of additional faculty development	612
5	build classrooms, because that’s what we need in our school. We have enough teachers but classroom that what we need.	Concern a authorities have to build classrooms and hire	Building classrooms	613

teachers to minimize
the burden of teachers
and students in over-
sized class

The table 6 shows the gathered data from shared experiences of the participants on effects of over-sized class to the teaching performance of teachers. There are five clustered themes emerged from significant statements of participants coded as 611-615.

Three out five participants coded as 611 with emergent theme of building enough classrooms and hiring more teachers. This means that building enough classrooms and hiring more teachers is the solutions to the issues of over-sized class. This implies that teachers suggested that building enough classrooms and hiring more teachers is the solutions to the issues of over-sized class. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participants 1, 2 and 3 “I think to address this issues, our authorities should build more buildings and hire teachers so that, the burden of teachers will be lessen. Buildings and teachers are the only solutions”; “provide classrooms and teachers, why? Because if ever we have more classrooms and teachers, then we can divide over-sized classes. It will less burdens for the teachers”; and “if they could provide us enough classrooms then better because that what students need so far of course teachers as well”.

One out of five participant coded as 612 with emergent theme of building classrooms and provision of additional free faculty development. This means that building classrooms and provision of additional free faculty development is the solutions to the issues of over-sized class. This implies that the government may build classrooms and provision of additional free faculty development to lessen the over-sized class. This is further supported by the actual statements of the participant 4, “Okay to be honest, to those concern heads and authorities, they should give priorities in building classrooms and hiring more teachers so that we can follow the ideal number of students per classroom, by that way (pwede na natin e) apply yung we can apply that teaching approach that we want, execute fun learning activities. So if they want quality education then they should provide what is lacking in the school. (Syempre add to mo na din ang) of course you also add the free professional growth trainings for teachers because we really need that because we are molding young minds and the hope of future of the nation”.

One out of five participant coded as 613 with emergent theme of building classrooms. This means that building classrooms are the solutions in over-sized class in their school. This implies that building classrooms are the solutions in over-sized class. These will help in reducing the burden of teachers and students.

Indeed, Meador (2019) believed that in a crowded classroom, teaching can be difficult, unpleasant, and frustrating. The challenges posed by a packed classroom can make even the most experienced teachers feel overburdened. Many schools nowadays must have the tough decision of increasing class sizes in order to remain open due to inadequate funding.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings, it is concluded that most of the participants encountered difficulties in teaching over-sized class which negatively affects the teaching performance and learning of the students despite the multiple strategies they employed in teaching.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended: Teachers may strictly impose classroom rules and regulations at the beginning of the class. Teachers may think of effective teaching strategies that will satisfy the learning needs of the students. The teachers may employ evaluation techniques that will measure the validity and reliability of learning of students. School head teachers may conduct seminars, trainings and workshops enhancing teachers’ classroom management and teaching strategies. Teachers may know how to manage their emotions especially when teaching and facing a large number of misbehaving students inside the classroom. The Government may providing a suitable educational infrastructure, particularly classrooms that adhere to government standards. Further research could be conducted using other fields of disciplines and methods of research to find solutions to the concerns of over-sized class.

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